

Appendix S1. Sequence ID; Taxon (accepted); Locality; Voucher (Herbarium); Sequence data: ndhF, rpoC2, trnT-L-F, rbcL, matK, rpl32, ETS, ITS, PPR24, PPR62, PPR70, PPR123, waxy haplotype 1, waxy haplotype 2. Genbank numbers are reported for sequence data generated by previous studies, hyphens indicate missing data, and asterisks indicate sequences generated for this study. Sequence data are available in their respective alignments on Dryad: <https://doi.org/10.5061/dryad.31zcrjdk6>.

Baillonia_amabilis_MC4522; *Baillonia amabilis* Bocq. Ex Baill.; Bolivia; M. Cardenas 4522 (US); *,*,*,*,*,-,-,-,-,-,-,-,-,-,-. C_affine_TW3014; *Citharexylum affine* D.Don; Mexico; T. Wendt et al. 3014 (F); *,*,*,*,*,*,-,-,-,-,-,-,-,-,-,-. C_affine_V6743; *Citharexylum affine* D.Don; Mexico; Villanueva 6743 (MEXU); *,*,*,*,*,*,-,-,-,-,-,-,-,-,-,-. C_affine_VS; *Citharexylum affine* D.Don; Mexico; E. Velasco-Sinaca 620 (MEXU); *,*,*,*,*,*,-,-,-,-,-,-,-,-,-,-. C_alainii_VSR2959A; *Citharexylum alainii* Moldenke; Dominican Republic; Veloz, Salazar, & Reyes 2959-A (FTG); *,*,*,*,*,*,-,-,-,-,-,-,-,-,-,-. C_altamiranum_EC2609; *Citharexylum altamiranum* Greenm.; Mexico; E. Carranza 2609 (MEXU); *,*,*,*,*,*,-,-,-,-,-,-,-,-,-,-. C_altamiranum_GJD9971; *Citharexylum altamiranum* Greenm.; Mexico; G. & J. Davidse 9971 (MO); *,*,*,*,*,-,-,-,-,-,-,-,-,-,-. C_altamiranum_M12032; *Citharexylum altamiranum* Greenm.; Mexico; R.H. Magaña 12032 (MEXU); *,*,*,*,*,*,-,-,-,-,-,-,-,-,-,-. C_altamiranum_OH9864; *Citharexylum altamiranum* Greenm.; Mexico; Orozoco H. 9864 (MEXU); -,-,-,-,-,-,-,-,-,-,-,-,-,-,-,-. C_altamiranum_RH4704; *Citharexylum altamiranum* Greenm.; Mexico; R. Hernandez 4704 (MO); *,*,*,*,-,-,-,-,-,-,-,-,-,-. C_andinum_F2628; *Citharexylum andinum* Moldenke; Bolivia; E. Fernandez et al. 2628 (MO); *,*,*,*,*,-,-,-,-,-,-,-,-,-,-. C_argutedentatum_RGO09_32; *Citharexylum argutedentatum* Moldenke; Peru; R.G. Olmstead 2009-32 (WTU); *,*,*,*,-,-,-,-,-,-,-,-,-,-. C_argutedentatum_RGO09_36; *Citharexylum argutedentatum* Moldenke; Peru; R.G. Olmstead 2009-36 (WTU); *,*,*,*,*,*,-,-,-,-,-,-,-,-,-,-. C_berlandieri_FTG; *Citharexylum berlandieri* S.Watson; USA; cultivated; *,*,*,*,*,*,-,-,-,-,-,-,-,-,-,-. C_berlandieri_JT674; *Citharexylum berlandieri* S.Watson; United States; J. Trusty 674 (FTG); -,-,-,-,-,-,-,-,-,-,-,-,-,-,-,-. C_berlandieri_LAF65; *Citharexylum berlandieri* S.Watson; Mexico; L.A. Frost 65 (WTU); *,*,*,*,*,*,-,-,-,-,-,-,-,-,-,-. C_berlandieri_RHM11926; *Citharexylum berlandieri* S.Watson; Mexico; R.H. Magaña 11926 (MEXU); *,*,*,*,*,*,-,-,-,-,-,-,-,-,-,-. C_bourgeauianum_W20066; *Citharexylum bourgeauianum* Greenm.; Mexico; Webster et al 20066 (GH); -,-,-,-,-,-,-,-,-,-,-,-,-,-,-,-. C_brachyanthum_FC9112; *Citharexylum brachyanthum* (A.Gray ex Hemsl.) A. Gray; Mexico; F. Chiang 9112 (F); *,*,*,*,*,*,-,-,-,-,-,-,-,-,-,-. C_brachyanthum_JAE2609; *Citharexylum brachyanthum* (A.Gray ex Hemsl.) A. Gray; Mexico; J.A. Encina 2609 (MEXU); *,*,*,*,-,-,-,-,-,-,-,-,-,-. C_brachyanthum_JWC11623; *Citharexylum brachyanthum* (A.Gray ex Hemsl.) A. Gray; Mexico; Johnston, Wendt, Chiang 11623 (F); *,*,*,*,-,-,-,-,-,-,-,-,-,-. C_brachyanthum_RTC17479; *Citharexylum brachyanthum* (A.Gray ex Hemsl.) A. Gray; Mexico; R.T. Colín 17479 (MEXU); *,*,*,*,-,-,-,-,-,-,-,-,-,-. C_calvum_MSEC12309; *Citharexylum calvum* Moldenke; Mexico; M. Sousa S. & E.F. Cabrera C. 12309 (MO); -,-,-,-,-,-,-,-,-,-,-,-,-,-,-,-. C_calvum_LAF79; *Citharexylum calvum* Moldenke; Mexico; L.A. Frost 79 (WTU); *,*,*,*,*,*,-,-,-,-,-,-,-,-,-,-. C_calvum_LAF80; *Citharexylum calvum* Moldenke; Mexico; L.A. Frost 80 (WTU); *,*,*,*,*,*,-,-,-,-,-,-,-,-,-,-. C_caudatum_CSM2352; *Citharexylum caudatum* L.; Dominican Republic; Santana Montilla Clase 2352 (FTG); *,*,*,*,-,-,-,-,-,-,-,-,-,-. C_caudatum_RGO96_73; *Citharexylum caudatum* L.; Cuba; R.G. Olmstead 1996-73A (WTU); *,*,*,*,*,*,-,-,-,-,-,-,-,-,-,-. C_cooperi_BH25538; *Citharexylum cooperi* Standl.; Costa Rica; B. Hammel 25538 (INB); *,*,*,*,*,*,-,-,-,-,-,-,-,-,-,-. C_costaricense_E626; *Citharexylum costaricense* Moldenke; Costa Rica; R.E. Espinoza O. 626 (MO); *,*,*,-,-,-,-,-,-,-,-,-,-.

Citharexylum peruvianum N. O'Leary; Peru; *L.A. Frost* 123 (WTU); *,*,*,*,*,*,*,*,*,*,*,*. C_peruvianum_LAF99; *Citharexylum peruvianum* N. O'Leary; Peru: La Libertad; *L.A. Frost* 99 (WTU); *,*,*,*,*,*,*,*,*,*,*,*. C_peruvianum_S17122; *Citharexylum peruvianum* N. O'Leary; Peru; *Segasteguii* 17122 (USM); *,*,*,*,*,*,*,*,*,*,*,*. C_poeppigii_LAF13_11; *Citharexylum poeppigii* Walp.; Colombia; *L.A. Frost* 13-11 (WTU); *,*,*,*,*,*,*,*,*,*,*,*. C_poeppigii_LAF13_12; *Citharexylum poeppigii* Walp.; Colombia; *L.A. Frost* 13-12 (WTU); *,*,*,*,*,*,*,*,*,*,*,*. C_racemosum_M5997; *Citharexylum racemosum* Sessé & Moc.; Mexico; *Martinez* 5997; *,*,*,*,*,*,*,*,*,*,*,*. C_reticulatum_AA581; *Citharexylum reticulatum* Kunth; Bolivia; *A. Araijo et al.* 581 (MO); -, -, -, -, -, *, -, -, -, -, -, -. C_rimbachii_LAF138; *Citharexylum rimbachii* Moldenke; Ecuador; *L.A. Frost* 138 (WTU); *,*,*,*,*,*,*,*,*,*,*,*. C_rimbachii_LAF139; *Citharexylum rimbachii* Moldenke; Ecuador; *L.A. Frost* 139 (WTU); *,*,*,*,*,*,*,*,*,*,*,*. C_rosei_CWJ8180; *Citharexylum rosei* Greenm.; Mexico; *Chiang, Wendt, & Johnston* 8180 (F); *,*,*,*,*,*,*,*,*,*,*,*. C_roxanae_AC5083; *Citharexylum roxanae* Moldenke; Mexico: Baja California Sur; *A. Carter* 5083 (F); *,*,*,*,*,*,*,*,*,*,*,*. C_roxanae_RM23834; *Citharexylum roxanae* Moldenke; Mexico; *R. Moran* 23834 (MO); *,*,*,*,*,*,*,*,*,*,*,*. C_scabrum_F359_94; *Citharexylum scabrum* Moc. & Sessé ex D. Don; Mexico; *S. L. Friedman, J. D. Freeh & Santos Buitimea-Anguamea* 359-94 (MEXU); *,*,*,*,*,*,*,*,*,*,*,*. C_schottiiCR_LAF14_04; *Citharexylum schottii* Greenm.; Costa Rica; *L.A. Frost* 14-04 (WTU); *,*,*,*,*,*,*,*,*,*,*,*. C_schottiiCR_LAF14_07; *Citharexylum schottii* Greenm.; Costa Rica; *L.A. Frost* 14-07 (WTU); *,*,*,*,*,*,*,*,*,*,*,*. C_schottiiCR_LAF14_09; *Citharexylum schottii* Greenm.; Costa Rica; *L.A. Frost* 14-09 (WTU); *,*,*,*,*,*,*,*,*,*,*,*. C_schottiiMEX_LAF62; *Citharexylum schottii* Greenm.; Mexico; *L.A. Frost* 62 (WTU); *,*,*,*,*,*,*,*,*,*,*,*. C_schottiiMEX_LAF63; *Citharexylum schottii* Greenm.; Mexico; *L.A. Frost* 63 (WTU); *,*,*,*,*,*,*,*,*,*,*,*. C_solanaceum_RW341; *Citharexylum solanaceum* Cham.; Brazil; *R. Wasum* 341 (MO); *,*,*,*,*,*,*,*,*,*,*,*. C_spinosum_JCS5727; *Citharexylum spinosum* L.; USA: Puerto Rico; *J.C. Solomon* 5727 (TEX); *,*,*,*,*,*,*,*,*,*,*,*. C_spinosum_RGO14_04; *Citharexylum spinosum* L.; United States; *R.G. Olmstead* 2014-04 (WTU); *,*,*,*,*,*,*,*,*,*,*,*. C_spinosum_RGO96_113; *Citharexylum spinosum* L.; Cuba; *R.G. Olmstead* 1996-113 (WTU); *,*,*,*,*,*,*,*,*,*,*,*. C_standleyi_AM3011; *Citharexylum standleyi* Moldenke; Mexico; *A. Magallanes* 3011 (F); *,*,*,*,*,*,*,*,*,*,*,*. C_standleyi_L1796; *Citharexylum standleyi* Moldenke; Mexico; *E.J. Lott* 1796 (MEXU); *,*,*,*,*,*,*,*,*,*,*,*. C_standleyi_LAPJ2182b; *Citharexylum standleyi* Moldenke; Mexico; *L. Alfredo Pérez J.* 2182b (MEXU); *,*,*,*,*,*,*,*,*,*,*,*. C_steyermarkii_DEB40360; *Citharexylum steyermarkii* Moldenke; Mexico; *D.E. Breedlove* 40360 (MO); *,*,*,*,*,*,*,*,*,*,*,*. C_subflavescens_LAF13_01; *Citharexylum subflavescens* S.F.Blake; Colombia; *L.A. Frost* 13-01 (WTU); *,*,*,*,*,*,*,*,*,*,*,*. C_subflavescens_LAF13_06; *Citharexylum subflavescens* S.F.Blake; Colombia; *L.A. Frost* 13-06 (WTU); *,*,*,*,*,*,*,*,*,*,*,*. C_subflavescens_LAF13_27; *Citharexylum subflavescens* S.F.Blake; Colombia; *L.A. Frost* 13-27 (WTU); *,*,*,*,*,*,*,*,*,*,*,*. C_subthyrsoideum_MGG30; *Citharexylum subthyrsoideum* Pittier; Venezuela; *M. Gabriela Gomez* 30 (MO); *,*,*,*,*,*,*,*,*,*,*,*. C_sulcatum_LAF13_07B; *Citharexylum sulcatum* Moldenke; Colombia; *L.A. Frost* 13-07 B (WTU); *,*,*,*,*,*,*,*,*,*,*,*. C_sulcatum_LAF13_08; *Citharexylum sulcatum* Moldenke; Colombia; *L.A. Frost* 13-08 (WTU); *,*,*,*,*,*,*,*,*,*,*,*. C_tetramerum_M8638; *Citharexylum tetramerum* Brandegee; Mexico; *A. García Mendoza & S. Franco* 8638 (MEXU); *,*,*,*,*,*,*,*,*,*,*,*. C_tetramerum_PT4717; *Citharexylum tetramerum* Brandegee; Mexico; *P. Teuoria* 4717 (F); *,*,*,*,*,*,*,*,*,*,*,*. C_tristachyum_G11484; *Citharexylum tristachyum* Turcz.; United States; *Gillis* 11484 (FTG); -, -, -

,-, -, -, -, *, *, -, -, -, C_ulei_LAF128; *Citharexylum ulei* Moldenke; Ecuador; *L.A. Frost 128* (WTU); *, *, *, *, *, *, *, *, *, *, *, *, -, -, C_ulei_LAF130; *Citharexylum ulei* Moldenke; Ecuador; *L.A. Frost 130* (WTU); *, *, *, *, *, *, *, *, *, *, *, *, -, *, C_weberbaueri_LAF103; *Citharexylum weberbaueri* Hayek; Peru; *L.A. Frost 103* (WTU); *, *, *, *, *, *, *, -, -, -, -, C_weberbaueri_LAF105; *Citharexylum weberbaueri* Hayek; Peru; *L.A. Frost 105* (WTU); *, *, *, *, *, *, *, *, *, *, *, *, -, *, *, *. C_weberbaueri_LAF106; *Citharexylum weberbaueri* Hayek; Peru; *L.A. Frost 106* (WTU); *, *, *, *, *, *, *, *, -, *, C_weberbaueri_LAF120; *Citharexylum weberbaueri* Hayek; Peru; *L.A. Frost 120* (WTU); *, *, *, *, *, *, *, *, -, -, -, -, C_weberbaueri_LAF124; *Citharexylum weberbaueri* Hayek; Peru; *L.A. Frost 124* (WTU); *, *, *, *, *, *, *, *, -, *, *, C_weberbaueri_LAF125; *Citharexylum weberbaueri* Hayek; Peru; *L.A. Frost 125* (WTU); *, *, *, *, *, *, *, *, -, *, *, *. C_weberbaueri_LAF126; *Citharexylum weberbaueri* Hayek; Peru; *L.A. Frost 126* (WTU); *, *, *, *, *, *, *, *, -, *, *, C_weberbaueri_PLI09_04; *Citharexylum weberbaueri* Hayek; Peru; *P. Lu-Irving 2009-04* (WTU); *, *, *, *, *, *, *, *, -, *, *, *, *, *. *Rehdera penninervia* CLEC19938; *Rehdera penninervia* Moldenke; Guatemala; *C.L. Lundell & E. Contreras 19938* (TEX); *, *, *, *, *, *, *, *, -, -, -, -, *Rehdera penninervia* MPCNB1378; *Rehdera penninervia* Moldenke; Guatemala; *M. Pena-Chocarro & N. Bonilla 1378* (MO); *, *, *, *, *, *, *, *, -, *, *, *, *. *Rehdera trinervis* DN2386; *Rehdera trinervis* Moldenke; Nicaragua; *D. Neil 2386* (MO); *, *, *, *, *, *, *, *, -, -, *, *, *. *Rehdera trinervis* EMS30531; *Rehdera trinervis* Moldenke; MX; *E. Martinez S. 30531* (TEX); *, *, *, *, *, *, *, *, -, -, *, *, *.

Outgroups:

Casselia glaziovii MAS3630; *Casselia glaziovii* (Briq. & Moldenke) Moldenke; Brazil; *M. Aparecidada Silena et al. 3630* (US); HM216698, HM853941, HM216603, HM8538915, HM853883, *, *, *, -, FJ549157, -, FJ549291, *, *. *Duranta vestita* MRRW50; *Duranta vestita* Cham.; Brazil; *M. Rossato & R. Wasum 50* (MO); *, *, *, *, *, *, *, *, -, *, *, *, *. *Hierbotana inflata* JH6199; *Hierbotana inflata* (Kunth) Briq.; Ecuador; *J. Humbles 6199* (TEX); *, *, *, *, *, *, *, *, -, -, -, -, -. *Lampayo castellani* RGO07_63; *Lampayo castellani* Moldenke; Argentina; *R.G. Olmstead 2007-63* (WTU); HM216736, HM853933, HM216630, HM853906, HM853874, *, MN019138, MN065668, -, FJ549144, FJ549189, FJ549278, *, *. *Lantana depressa* PLI12_01; *Lantana depressa* Small; United States (cultivated); *P. Lu-Irving 2012-01* (WTU); *, *, *, *, *, KX827925, *, KX827995, *, -, KX833332, -, -. *Nashia inaguensis* WTG13097; *Nashia inaguensis* Millsp.; Bahamas; *William T. Gillis 13097* (TEX); *, *, *, *, *, *, *, *, -, *, *, *, -, -, -. *Pitreaa cuneato-ovata* (Cav.) Caro; Argentina; *R.G. Olmstead 2004-186* (WTU); HM216768, HM853937, HM216661, HM853910, HM853878, *, *, *, -, FJ549146, FJ549191, FJ549280, -, -. *Recordia boliviana* NRJW2932; *Recordia boliviana* Moldenke; Bolivia; *N. Ritter & J. Wood 2932* (MO); *, *, *, *, *, *, *, *, -, *, *, *. *Verbena officinalis* RGO03_156; *Verbena officinalis* L.; United States (cultivated); *R.G. Olmstead 2003-156* (WTU); *, *, EF571525, HM853899, HM853866, JX966897, *, *, -, FJ549118, FJ549163, FJ549252, -, -.